

transformation that exposes them to new values and a renewed identity as young adults, preparing to be global citizens and informed leaders, hopefully motivated by a concern for the common good.

This year 2025 Papua New Guinea celebrate 50 years as an Independent nation. Just recently, Divine Word University invited one of the founders of the PNG constitution, John Momis, to address them so that they as modern students could recall the ideals that inspired the founding generation of their country. This year the theme of the university is "Living our noble traditions and the Christian principles". Those were the ideals from the founding generation, enshrined in the Preamble to the Papua New Guinea Constitution.

As PNG looks to the future, strengthening higher education means reinforcing the trust, purpose, and transformative power of the University to build a better nation.

15 Trust through Open Science

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There is comfort in realizing high public trust in science and scholarship. Contrary to some narratives on reducing trust in science, it remains high and is higher than in other public institutions such as

politics, law and journalism. Since the COVID pandemic trust in science has even grown, presumably due to the fast development of vaccines. This is the outcome from surveys in the Netherlands¹, and judging from a literature review, these findings are similar in many countries and regions².

A deeper analysis shows a more nuanced story. There are differences in opinion and it depends on the persons you ask these questions. Those with higher levels of education, higher income and with a more progressive political preference have more trust in science. In fact, apart from rising trust in general, skewness increases with distrust increasing by some and trust increasing by others, mirroring the political and societal polarization that is visible in the global north.

Also, topic-wise clear differences become visible. There is high trust in technology and medicine. These domains are known to provide more ready-made solutions, products and services to the benefit of society such as in public health and the energy transition. Trust is less so in scientists and scholars addressing complex societal issues such as inequality, poverty, and

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democracy. This reflects a utilitarian view on universities where the sciences are sometimes seen to be more useful compared to the humanities, and less so, the social sciences. Such a view goes beyond the role of universities as institutions of liberal education and research where scholarly and scientific enquiry is open-ended. Universities are not defined by the questions they ask and the answers they provide, but by their methods: the way they ask questions and how they address them. For this reason along science and scholarship is never done.

A third relevant observation is that both universities, as institutions and their staff, are highly trusted. However, the impact of their activities on policies to address and contribute to solutions for complex societal challenges, through a science-policy interface, is not that well trusted by people. This interface can even be institutionalized, such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change which is a science-policy interface in my own field, providing scientific evidence and solutions to combat climate change. However, the efficacy of such boundary objects is questioned and may not provide sufficient agency to citizens. These three observations may guide universities in strategies and policies to increase trust.

It is good to realize that trust is relational. Trust implies a dependency and recognition of expertise of the other and this means that vulnerability must be accepted. To maintain and increase trust within and outside universities the reciprocal relations between scientists and scholars within academia and the relation between science and society needs consideration and scrutiny. I argue that these two main issues can be addressed with open science and open education. First, open science transforms scientific and scholarly enquiry and the sharing of knowledge. Second, open science enables science and scholarship to be transdisciplinary, which is needed to realize a true reciprocal relationship between science and society and in that way builds trust and that acknowledges that the position of the university is also cultural.

At universities expertise is expressed and recognized by deep knowledge and understanding that should be scrutinized through the rigor, accuracy, precision and openness to criticism. There is no individual academic that can reach such a deep level of expertise that they can oversee it all. This is especially clear for inter- and transdisciplinary studies where various strands of knowledge are needed to address societal issues. This is also true within disciplines because of the complexity of science and methodologies that are used. This implies that within academia trust in one-another is essential to collaborate and make progress.

1. See report from Rathenau Institute, in Dutch: [Vertrouwen in de wetenschap 2025 | Rathenau Instituut](#)

2. For instance, recent paper by Cologna *et al* 2025: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-02090-5>

This also means that at universities we should stay true to the aforementioned qualities of rigor, precision etc. within and between disciplines. Open science enables that. It opens up scientific knowledge in the widest possible sense, from open access articles, to open source software, to open access to research infrastructures. In this way it leads to more transparent and therefore trustworthy science. When implemented globally, it will lead to more accessible science and education which spurs new intellectual enquiry from a wide range of perspectives, including those from the global south and north.

However, this is not enough. If there is a trust-crisis reported in literature, it has primarily to do with the relation between science, scholarship, and society at large. Universities need to open up to wider society and collaborate more with societal actors, including connecting to its polarized edges, and to accept wider criticism from those edges. Only in this way reciprocal strategies and policies can be developed accordingly that leads to trust. Universities shouldn't shy away from complex societal issues, but rather engage with relevant actors to address them. Not by providing final answers, but in reflecting on the past, providing solutions and imagining hopeful and better futures, knowing that these solutions will be intermediate, that they will be reflected upon again, using rigor, accuracy and precision. No doubt it will be challenging because it comes with normative and ethical considerations. But even those should continuously be challenged.

This goes beyond disciplined research because universities are institutions where the talented youth is educated to play a role in society later in their careers. Universities are places where not only knowledge is transferred, but where also socialization takes place to transfer civic values to the benefit of society. So, like research, open education has an important role in building trust between universities and society at large.

This is what open science and, indeed, open education should be about. Openness within and between institutions to increase the quality scientific and scholarly enquiry. However, more importantly, openness towards the wider society including the polarized edges. It needs open and disciplined scholarship and science, realizing the role of universities within society.

16 Rebuilding Trust in Higher Education: A View from Nigeria

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Higher education used to be a ray of hope for people all over the world, a means of achieving both individual and societal progress.

“Higher education must be rethought as a transformational force to be rebuilt rather than as a dysfunctional institution to be endured.”

Today, the growing mistrust of the people causes that beacon to flicker. Mistrust of higher education is also highly evident in Nigeria. Despite South Africa's higher tertiary enrolment, Nigeria has the most comprehensive higher education system in Sub-Saharan Africa, with more institutions (Oladipo, 2019). Nigeria's larger population and decentralised education system contribute to its higher number of institutions. However, South Africa often ranks higher in global university rankings due to stronger infrastructure and research output. Nigerian universities have historically taken great pleasure in being Ivory Towers. However, it is becoming more difficult to overlook the Ivory Towers' systemic flaws.

The Debacle of Trust

The root cause of the mistrust in Nigerian higher education is a complicated network of structural shortcomings:

The corruption of academia: Academic fraud has grown alarmingly commonplace, ranging from exam malfeasance to credential fraud. Numerous sexcapades of instructors in higher education institutes are widely reported in the media. In 2019, the Africa Eye programme of the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) sent undercover journalists posing as students to capture footage of the sexual harassment and what goes on behind the closed doors of some of the most prestigious universities in West Africa (Kiki Mordi, 2019). Public suspicion was also heightened by a recent incident involving phoney degrees from foreign universities, which led to the delisting of 18 foreign university campuses in Nigeria (Tolu-Kolawole, 2024).

Underfunding and declining infrastructure: Many institutions struggle with inadequate funding, packed classrooms, and dilapidated infrastructure. Despite their renown, several first- and second-generation institutions suffer from infrastructure deficiencies that compromise the educational process.

Political interference and poor governance: Trust in institutional leadership and government control has been damaged by frequent strikes, postponed academic calendars, and opaque decision-making procedures.

Election fraud: based on their expertise, higher education instructors are seen as accountable, trustworthy, honest, and models of integrity. This is the justification for selecting them to act as election umpires; nonetheless, some of them have been found guilty of falsifying results (Lawal, 2025; Odili, 2025). This raises grave concerns for the credibility of the academics tasked with maintaining objectivity who are involved in manipulation.